

A Conjecture on the Hypothetical Possibility of Elementary Particles and Nuclei Behaving as Magnetic Monopoles and a Suggested Method for its Validation

Rao R. Morusupalli, Ph.D.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7188-5262>

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The material presented in this work is purely hypothetical, a conjecture, and needs further scientific validation. Orbital and spin angular momentums of elementary charged particles in an atom explain why an atom behaves as a tiny magnetic dipole rendering explanations for commonly observed phenomenon such as paramagnetism and ferromagnetism. So far, a magnetic monopole has not been observed. In this work we hypothesize that if the magnetism due to elementary particles in an atom is regarded as a magnetic monopole, it can be conjectured that such a supposition may still explain the generally accepted view of atoms behaving as tiny magnetic dipoles. A method is suggested as future work to validate the hypothesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

The nature of magnetism is not fully understood. Magnetic monopoles have not been shown to exist nor why a magnet behaves only as a dipole with its opposite and inseparable north(N) and a south(S) poles. Oersted, H.C. was the first to discover in 1820 that electric currents create magnetic fields[1]. Although it is generally accepted and demonstrated that electric charges exist as positive and negatively charged distinct types and that magnetic fields are produced when such charges are in motion, it is not well understood why a magnetic field created by either a moving positive or a moving negative charge creates only a magnetic dipole instead of a corresponding type of magnetic monopole. Much before Michael Faraday demonstrated[2] that magnetic fluids or monopoles do not exist, it was widely believed that magnetism is caused by oppositely charged magnetic fluids, just as electric charges, where each fluid was believed to have been due to oppositely charged magnetic molecules[3],[4],[5]. Some of the fundamental questions that arise with regards to our limited understanding of magnetism are as follows:

1. Why are electric charges found in nature as distinct positive and negative charges (electric monopoles) but magnetic monopoles are not?
2. Do magnetic monopoles exist in nature but manifest themselves so as not to be found as distinct and separate magnetic monopoles?
3. Is it possible that the observed behavior of atoms acting as tiny magnetic dipoles is due to a net effect of magnetism originating due to elementary particles within an atom behaving as a magnetic monopole?
4. Are there any ways to isolate or detect such magnetic monopoles due to sub-atomic particles, if hypothesized to exist within an atom?

It is the purpose of this work to try and answer these questions and to induce interest through a paradigm shift

for further research by proposing an alternate possibility for the creation of magnetic dipoles at an atomic level that could be based on magnetic monopoles due to sub-atomic elementary particles such as electrons and protons. It needs to be highlighted again that this work is a conjecture needing further scientific investigation and data for its validation.

II. A NOTE ON SYMMETRY IN NATURE

The role of symmetry in fundamental physics and its laws and equations is well known[6]. Symmetry is found in nature and has many examples in crystal and biological systems. There is symmetry in mathematical equations that model natural laws such as laws of motion and in quantum mechanics. The Maxwell's equations are almost symmetric but not completely.

Maxwell's equations as known today are:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \rho_e / \epsilon_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$-\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} + \mu_0 \mathbf{j}_e \quad (4)$$

where the electric quantities are \mathbf{E} , the electric field, the electric charge density ρ_e and the electric current density \mathbf{j}_e . The magnetic quantity is the magnetic field \mathbf{B} . ϵ_0 and μ_0 are the permittivity and permeability of free space, respectively. Milton, K.A. has provided a theoretical and experimental status of magnetic monopoles in 2006 where it is mentioned[4] that the obvious virtue of introducing a magnetic monopole would be a symmetry imparted to Maxwell's equations where such possible

symmetry does not exist in the equations as known today due to presumed zero divergence of the magnetic field as in Eq. (2). It follows from stated zero divergence of magnetic field that magnetic monopoles cannot exist. If the concept of zero divergence of a magnetic field were to be untrue then the symmetrical form of Maxwell's equations would look as follows:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \rho_e / \epsilon_0 \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \rho_m \quad (6)$$

$$-\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} + \mu_0 \mathbf{j}_m \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} + \mu_0 \mathbf{j}_e \quad (8)$$

While the original equations lack symmetry, the assumption of non-zero divergence of a magnetic field would impart symmetry by the introduction of magnetic equivalent of electric quantities, namely the magnetic charge density ρ_m and the magnetic current density \mathbf{j}_m as in Eqs. (6) and (7). Such magnetic quantities have so far never been shown to exist in nature.

III. MAGNETIC FIELD DUE TO AN ATOM

The current and generally accepted view of an atom is that of a tiny magnetic dipole.

Consider an electron orbiting in a circular motion and in a clockwise direction as illustrated in Fig.1. The electron orbital magnetic moment shown as μ_{eo} , is due to its charge and the orbital angular momentum.

FIG. 1. Orbital magnetic moment μ_{eo} of an isolated electron with charge e^- and mass m_e orbiting in a circular motion with radius R in a clockwise direction.

An electron that just spins around its own axis in a clockwise direction can be shown to have a spin magnetic moment as illustrated in Fig.2(a). A positive charge with a clockwise axial spin can be shown to have a spin magnetic moment as illustrated in Fig.2(b). Here

μ_{es} is the magnetic moment due to the negative charge (electron) spinning clockwise on its axis and μ_{ps} is the magnetic moment of a positive charge spinning clockwise on its axis. These arise due to their charge and spin angular momentums. An example of such a positive charge spinning on its axis could be a positively charged proton in an atomic nucleus[7]. In these systems, due to their intrinsic charge and orbital or spin angular momentums or both, they behave like tiny magnets with a north and a south pole, as illustrated. The net magnetic moment of the atom would be a vector sum of the magnetic moments due to its elementary particles and the overall atom also behaves like a tiny magnetic dipole. This is the current and generally accepted view for an atom behaving like a tiny magnetic dipole. Note that the magnetic moments of the overall nucleus would be due to both protons and neutrons but in this work we have ignored the contribution from neutrons that arise out of a quark model and therefore they are not in the illustrations, for simplicity. The hypothesis we present in this work would apply equally well to magnetic moments from the neutrons. Ignoring the magnetic moment due to neutrons does not alter our hypothesis and its predictions as described later in the following sections.

The natural unit for expressing the magnetic moments of an electron due to its orbital or spin angular momentum is the Bohr magneton μ_B which is defined in SI units as:

$$\mu_B = -\frac{e\hbar}{2m_e} \quad (9)$$

where, e is the elementary charge, \hbar is reduced *Planck* constant and m_e is the electron rest mass. The *Bohr magneton* has been shown to have a value of 9.274×10^{-24} Joule/Tesla[8]. The quantization of the orbital angular momentum results in the corresponding quantization of the orbital magnetic moment.

FIG. 2. Generally accepted view of spin magnetic moment μ (a) μ_{es} : an isolated negative charge (electron) spinning clockwise on its axis and (b) μ_{ps} : an isolated positive charge spinning clockwise on its axis.

The magnetic moment due to a spinning proton can also be expressed in terms of a nuclear magneton μ_N

which is defined in SI units as:

$$\mu_N = \frac{e\hbar}{2m_p} \quad (10)$$

where m_p is the proton rest mass. The nuclear magneton μ_N has a value of 5.050×10^{-27} Joule/Tesla[8] and the magnetic moment due to spin of a proton μ_{ps} has been shown to be given as:

$$\mu_{ps} = 2.793 \times \mu_N \quad (11)$$

IV. POSSIBILITY OF ELEMENTARY PARTICLES AS MAGNETIC MONOPOLES

Compton, A.H.[9] was of the first to suggest that an orbiting electron behaves like a tiny permanent magnet where he notes that *"Perhaps the most natural, and certainly the most generally accepted view of the nature of the elementary magnet, is that the revolution of electrons in orbits within the atom give to the atom as a whole the properties of a tiny permanent magnet"*. Prior to Compton, it was also the general belief that magnetic phenomenon could find an explanation through hypothesizing that matter could be made up of tiny magnetic particles or elementary magnets. In 1905 Langevin, P. proposed a kinetic theory of magnetism[10]. Further to this, Weiss, P. extended Langevin's hypothesis to ferromagnetic substances. A brief review of work by Langevin and Weiss that precedes that of Compton's work from 1921 is available in a 1917 review by Terry, E.M.[11]. Prior to all these works it was already assumed that magnetism exists as dipoles, as was established by Gauss's law of magnetism, followed by Maxwell's equations of 1862 which provided a mathematical form that showed that magnetic monopoles do not exist. One exception being that in 1894 Pierre Curie mentions the possibility of existence of monopoles[12]. Much later in 1931, Paul Dirac[13] showed that magnetic monopoles may exist if electric charge is quantized which is consistent with current understanding that charge is quantized but this is not sufficient to establish with certainty that monopoles exist. A magnetic monopole that could be explained by the law of charge quantization as formulated by Dirac has never been observed in real experiments[14],[15],[3]].

The idea of magnetic fields and magnetism as known today is primarily due to the atom behaving as a magnetic dipole while the scientific community continues to seek on the possibility of the existence of magnetic monopoles. We present an alternate hypothesized possibility based on elementary particles behaving as magnetic monopoles yet this possibility can provide an explanation for the accepted view of atoms behaving as tiny magnetic dipoles.

V. HYPOTHESIS AND PREDICTIONS

Before hypothesizing an alternate possibility we need to ask ourselves some additional questions:

1. Is the generally established and observed magnetic dipole moment of an atom really due to a vector sum of *magnetic dipole* moments of its constituent sub-atomic particles? Are there other possibilities?
2. What would be the validity of an assumption that a sub-atomic particle like an electron orbiting around the nucleus or spinning on its own axis behaves as a *magnetic monopole* rather than a dipole?
3. Can the observed behavior of an atom acting as a magnetic dipole be explained as the combined vector sum of magnetic moments due to distinct magnetic monopoles arising from elementary charged particles?

A. Hypothesis

"The magnetism due to an orbital or spin angular momentum of a charged elementary particle, such as an electron or a proton, acts like a magnetic monopole."

This is much contrary to current and generally accepted view of magnetism, as noted earlier, which is that of an electrically charged particle (an electric monopole) producing a magnetic dipole due to its angular momentums. However, we shall try to illustrate in this work about how a hypothesis of a magnetic monopole due to elementary particles can still predict a simple atom to behave like a net magnetic dipole (the magnetic dipole being the generally accepted view of the atom).

B. Predictions based on Hypothesis - Atoms

The hypothesis assumes the possibility that an electric charge can only produce a magnetic monopole due to its spin or orbital angular momentum, as illustrated in Fig.3. For illustration purpose we are showing that a negative charge spinning clockwise will result in a magnetic north pole while a positive charge with a clockwise spin direction will result in a magnetic south pole. Irrespective of the type of pole the prediction following the hypothesis is the possibility that negative and positive charges with similar spins shall result in opposite type of magnetic monopoles.

The hypothesis also predicts that a simple atomic structure with an electron orbiting in a clockwise direction and the nucleus of the atom with a single positive charge, such as a proton, spinning on its axis in a clockwise direction, will result in magnetic moments and monopoles as illustrated in Fig.4(a). Although consisting of elementary particles acting as magnetic monopoles,

FIG. 3. Hypothesized views: (a) An isolated negative charge spinning clockwise is hypothesized to result in a magnetic monopole N. (b) An isolated positive charge spinning clockwise is hypothesized to result in a magnetic monopole S.

the atom is shown to behave as a possible net magnetic dipole in Fig.4(b). The atom behaving as a tiny magnetic dipole is the current and generally accepted view.

FIG. 4. Hypothesized views: (a) An electron orbiting in a circle and simultaneously spinning clockwise on its axis is hypothesized to result in a magnetic monopole N and a total magnetic monopole moment of $\mu_{eo} + \mu_{es}$. A positive charge spinning clockwise on its axis is hypothesized to result in a magnetic monopole S and a magnetic moment μ_{ps} . (b) The monopoles as in (a) shown with hypothesized magnetic field lines that may behave like a net dipole.

Winkler et al.,[16] have shown the ratio of proton magneton to Bohr magneton to be about 1.52×10^{-3} and the ratio of Bohr magneton to proton magneton is its reciprocal with a value of 0.657×10^3 . If we assume that:

$$\mu_{eo} + \mu_{es} \approx \mu_B \quad (12)$$

then the ratio of the electron to the proton magnetic moments can be shown to be as:

$$\frac{\mu_{eo} + \mu_{es}}{\mu_{ps}} \approx \frac{\mu_B}{2.793 \times \mu_N} = 0.657 \times 10^3 \quad (13)$$

Our hypothesized view of the atom is then that of two magnetic monopoles with a ratio of their magnetic moments being in the order of about 650, yet the atom itself can still be considered to be a net magnetic dipole

due to the two distinct monopoles as hypothesized and illustrated in the Fig.4(a) and (b). It would therefore behave as a tiny magnetic dipole where one monopole is stronger than the other by a factor or approximately 650. We started off with a hypothesis that electric charges create magnetic monopoles yet such an assumption can still explain why an atom can behave like a tiny magnetic dipole although constituting two monopoles of unequal strengths.

C. Predictions based on Hypothesis - Bulk

Bulk magnetic materials, such as a bar magnet, behave as magnetic dipoles with equal and opposite pole strengths. How can the hypothetical model we have introduced for an atom behaving as a tiny magnetic dipole of unequal pole strengths support this observed behavior in bulk materials? An explanation for this could be that bulk material can be thought of as divided into small regions of magnetic domains where each domain is uniform within its own magnetic properties yet not across all domains. Magnetic domains is the generally accepted explanation for ferromagnetic behavior in materials[17]. While the magnetic pole strengths are unequal within a domain and different domains can maintain their own distinct spin directions and pole strengths, its possible that the net effect of all such domains may result in a combined bulk magnetism of equal and opposite magnetic pole strengths as illustrated in Fig.5. This possibility can be modeled using computer simulations and can be looked at as future work.

FIG. 5. Net effect of all such domains with dipoles of unequal pole strengths may result in a combined bulk material magnetism of equal and opposite magnetic pole strengths.

VI. A SUGGESTED METHOD TO VALIDATE THE HYPOTHESIS

A difference in magnitudes for magnetic monopole moments between N and S of the hypothesized atom can be detected by comparing the curvature of the paths traversed by a positive (or a negative) test charge moving

towards the atom. This is illustrated using a positive test charge in Fig.6 where it is expected that the radius of curvature R_1 to be less than that of the radius R_2 because the force on the moving test positive charge due to monopole N is expected to be higher than the force on an equivalent positive test charge passing near monopole S with a lesser magnetic moment.

FIG. 6. Hypothesized views for a suggested method: Comparison of the curvature of the paths traversed by a positive test charge moving towards the poles. Radius of curvature R_1 near the magnetic monopole N is expected to be less than the radius of curvature R_2 for an equivalent positive test charge passing near monopole S with a lesser magnetic moment.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work is a conjecture and not backed by experimental data or validation. While further research in this area is ongoing, we welcome feedback, comments and constructive criticism from the community in support of the spirit and movement of open science. The question that we ask here: “*Is it possible that magnetic monopoles could be around us at the sub-atomic level arising out of elementary charged particles, yet manifesting themselves as net magnetic dipoles at the atomic and bulk material level?*” The model of an atom behaving as a magnetic dipole is a generally accepted view to explain common phenomenon such as paramagnetism and ferromagnetism. If we hypothesize that the magnetism due to elementary charged particles produces a magnetic monopole due to their orbital or spin angular momentums, then we may predict that such an assumption may still explain the generally accepted view of an atom behaving like a tiny magnetic dipole. This suggestion is purely hypothetical and needs further validation.

We propose one method to verify the presented hypothesis and the possibility of showing that elementary charged particles may behave as magnetic monopoles. The generally accepted theory of magnetic domains may still be used to explain observed behavior of materials at the bulk level.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. C. Oersted, On electro-magnetism, *Annals of Philosophy* **2**, 321 (1821).
- [2] M. Faraday, *Experimental researches in electricity*-volume 3 (Taylor and Francis, 1855).
- [3] A. Rajantie, Introduction to magnetic monopoles, *Contemporary Physics* **53**, 195 (2012).
- [4] K. A. Milton, Theoretical and experimental status of magnetic monopoles, *Reports on Progress in Physics* **69**, 1637 (2006).
- [5] S. Balestra, G. Giacomelli, M. Giorgini, L. Patrizii, V. Popa, Z. Sahnoun, and V. Togo, Magnetic monopole bibliography-ii, arXiv preprint arXiv:1105.5587 (2011).
- [6] D. J. Gross, The role of symmetry in fundamental physics, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **93**, 14256 (1996).
- [7] E. Purcell and N. Ramsey, On the possibility of electric dipole moments for elementary particles and nuclei, *Physical Review* **78**, 807 (1950).
- [8] L. I. Schiff, *Quantum mechanics* (McGraw-Hill, 1955).
- [9] A. H. Compton, The magnetic electron, *Journal of the Franklin institute* **192**, 145 (1921).
- [10] P. Langevin, Sur la théorie du magnétisme, *J. Phys. Theor. Appl.* **4**, 678 (1905).
- [11] E. M. Terry, The magnetic properties of iron, nickel and cobalt above the curie point, and keeson’s quantum theory of magnetism, *Physical Review* **9**, 394 (1917).
- [12] P. Curie, On the possible existence of magnetic conductivity and free magnetism, *Seances Soc. Phys.(Paris)* **76** (1894).
- [13] P. A. M. Dirac, Quantised singularities in the electro-magnetic field, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character* **133**, 60 (1931).
- [14] E. Weinberg, Magnetic monopoles, .
- [15] B. Acharya, J. Alexandre, K. Bendtz, P. Benes, J. Bernabéu, M. Campbell, S. Cecchini, J. Chwastowski, A. Chatterjee, M. De Montigny, *et al.*, Search for magnetic monopoles with the moedal prototype trapping detector in 8 tev proton-proton collisions at the lhc, *Journal of High Energy Physics* **2016**, 1 (2016).
- [16] P. F. Winkler, D. Kleppner, T. Myint, and F. G. Walther, Magnetic moment of the proton in bohr magnetons, *Physical Review A* **5**, 83 (1972).
- [17] D. Craik and R. Tebble, Magnetic domains, *Reports on progress in physics* **24**, 116 (1961).